

ICR PROTOCOL

Integration will be conducted after completion of the independent quantitative and qualitative analyses and will be led by the principal investigator with active participation from the entire multidisciplinary research team. The integration process will form part of the planned analytical protocol and will be undertaken during structured consensus meetings in which quantitative results, qualitative themes, and representative quotations will be reviewed jointly.

Integration will be guided by the seven dimensions of the Birth Model Satisfaction Scale (BMSP2), which will serve as predefined points of connection between datasets. For each dimension, the team will examine the extent to which qualitative findings converge with, complement, expand, or contextualize the quantitative results. The objective of integration will not be to establish causal explanations, but rather to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of women's perceptions and experiences under the Integral Birth Model.

To guide integration, the research team will use a set of predefined analytical questions:

1. How do women's narratives relate to the quantitative findings observed in each BMSP2 dimension?
2. What contextual information do qualitative findings contribute to the interpretation of quantitative scores?
3. Which aspects of women's experiences are not fully represented within the quantitative instrument?
4. Do qualitative and quantitative findings show convergence, complementarity, expansion, or divergence?

An initial integration matrix will be developed by the principal investigator linking quantitative dimensions, qualitative categories, and representative quotations. This matrix will subsequently be reviewed by the entire research team through iterative discussion and consensus-building procedures. When differences between datasets are identified, these will not be treated as contradictions requiring resolution. Instead, they will be interpreted as complementary sources of evidence reflecting different dimensions of women's experiences. For example, if several quantitative dimensions demonstrate high satisfaction scores, qualitative findings will provide additional detail regarding communication processes, postpartum experiences, and contextual aspects of cesarean birth that may not be fully captured by the survey instrument. These insights will be incorporated into the final interpretation to enrich understanding of the phenomenon under study.

Integrated findings will ultimately be presented through joint displays in accordance with GRAMMS recommendations for mixed methods research.

MEETING MINUTES TEMPLATE - ICR PROTOCOL

INITIAL CALIBRATION MEETING MINUTES

Date: _____

Time: _____

Location: _____

Meeting modality: In-person Virtual Hybrid

ATTENDEES

Name Role Attendance

Principal Investigator Yes No

Midwife specialist Yes No

Expert Midwife Yes No

Statistician Yes No

Nurse midwife Yes No

Yes No

AGENDA

1. Codebook V1.0 Review
2. Calibration subsample discussion
3. Independent coding of 3 interviews
4. Initial discrepancies analysis
5. Refinement of definitions and criteria
6. Integración de resultados cualitativos
7. Integration of quantitative and qualitative results

AGREEMENTS REACHED

Discrepancias identificadas en la codificación:

1. Category: _____

· Discrepancy: _____

· Agreement: _____

2. Category: _____

· Discrepancy: _____

· Agreement: _____

Modifications to the Codebook:

· Definition updated for: _____

· Examples added to: _____

· Criteria clarified for: _____

PENDING ACTIONS

Responsible Task Deadline

Distribute Codebook V1.1

Schedule next meeting

Prepare Kappa subsample

Next meeting: _____

Signature of the Principal Investigator: _____

KAPPA CONSENSUS MEETING MINUTES

Date: _____

Time: _____

Reason: Analysis of Kappa results and code refinement

KAPPA RESULTS PRESENTED

Global Kappa Obtained: _____

Interpretation: Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

¿Cumple umbral mínimo (0.61)? Yes No

ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMATIC CATEGORIES

Categoría Kappa Obtained Identified Problems Agreed Solutions

DECISIONS MADE

- _____ categories kept without changes
- _____ categories modified
- _____ categories deleted
- _____ new categories added

AGREEMENTS FOR CODEBOOK V2.0

1. ---

2. ---

3. ---

ACTION PLAN

- Update Codebook to V2.0 (Responsible: _____)
- Train the whole team (Date: _____)
- Start full coding (Date: _____)

Signature of the Analysis Coordinator: _____

COHEN'S KAPPA COEFFICIENT CALCULATION MATRIX

MATRIX 1: RAW CODING DATA

Interview: _____

Coders: A = _____ B = _____

Segment Code Applied by A Code Applied by B Concordance

1 Yes No

2 Yes No

3 Yes No

4 Yes No

5 Yes No

6 Yes No

7 Yes No

8 Yes No

9 Yes No

10 Yes No

Total, de segments: _____

Observed concordances: _____

MATRIX 2: KAPPA CALCULATION PER CATEGORY

Category: _____

CONTINGENCY TABLE

Coder B: Yes Coder B: No Total

Coder A: Yes a = _____ b = _____ a+b = _____

Coder A: No c = _____ d = _____ c+d = _____

Total a+c = _____ b+d = _____ N = _____

APPLIED FORMULAS

Observed agreement proportion (Po):

$P_o = (a + d) / N =$ _____

Expected agreement proportion (Pe):

$P_e = [(a+b)(a+c) + (c+d)(b+d)] / N^2 =$ _____

Kappa Coefficient (κ):

$\kappa = (P_o - P_e) / (1 - P_e) =$ _____

Interpretation: Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

MATRIX 3: GLOBAL KAPPA SUMMARY

Calculation Date: _____

Total sample analyzed: _____ interviews (_____ segments)

Thematic Category Kappa Interpretación Observations

Cuidado Relacional de la Calidad Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

Autocuidado y Confort Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

Contacto Madre-Hijo Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

Despersonalización de la Atención Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

Participación Familiar Continua Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

Cuidado Oportuno y Respetuoso Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

Ambiente Físico Comfortable Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

WEIGHTED AVERAGE KAPPA

Formula: global $\kappa = \Sigma(\kappa_i \times n_i) / N$ total

Result: _____

Global interpretation: Poor Fair Moderate Good Excellent

RECOMMENDATIONS BASED ON RESULTS

- Proceed with full coding ($\kappa \geq 0.61$)
- Perform new calibration round ($\kappa < 0.61$)
- Review categories with $\kappa < 0.41$
- Maintain current protocol

MATRIX 4: DISCREPANCY LOG

Categoría Type of Discrepancy Frequency Agreed Resolution

Ambiguous definition

Code overlap

Application criteria

Thematic limits

Others: _____

DISCREPANCY PATTERN ANALYSIS

Most frequent discrepancies:

1. _____ (_____ occurrences)
2. _____ (_____ occurrences)
3. _____ (_____ occurrences)

Identified factors:

- Coder fatigue
- Segment complexity
- ambigüedad en definiciones
- Categorical overlap
- Others: _____